

METHODS OF TEACHING LANGUAGE THROUGH READING IN THE ORIGINAL (ILYA FRANK)

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ABSTRACT

Reading is an important part of learning any foreign language. As the student is acquainted with books, he expands his vocabulary and studies the main structures of the language. This paper examines the methodology of teaching language through reading in the original, developed by philologist Ilya Frank. Frank's method is based on the study of authentic texts in the target language. Gradually increasing the complexity of texts allows students to master vocabulary, grammar and develop reading skills. Analyzing and discussing what you read helps improve your oral and written communication skills. The Frank Method is an effective tool for language learning. When used correctly, it can improve the quality of learning and make it more interesting for students. This article also explains the advantages of method and its disadvantages. The result of the study is presented in the form of a diagram.

Introduction. Learning a foreign language is a complex and multifaceted process that requires an integrated approach. One of the effective learning methods is reading texts in the target language.

There are many methods of teaching a foreign language, and today everyone can choose a convenient format for himself or herself. As a rule, all of them are based on a consistent study of the structure of the language, the rules of grammar, memorization of words and development of speaking skills. Ilya Frank's reading method is the author's method based on reading adapted and non-adapted texts with parallel translation. Ilya Frank is a Russian philologist, translator and teacher, a graduate of Lomonosov Moscow State University. In 1999, to teach reading to his students, he adapted the book in German in an unusual format. It was Erich Kästner's work "Emil and the Detectives". The author's new method turned out to be so productive that soon his manual began to be used to teach different languages. [1]

Since 2001, many books have been published, adapted by Ilya Frank's method.

Currently, you can find more than 300 such reading aids, published in 59 languages.

Because of reading a large number of texts, the student develops a feeling foreign language, due to which the negative influence of the native language is weakened, which makes it easier and accelerates the subsequent development of oral speech.[4]

By reading students' active and passive vocabulary is enriched, grammatical skills.

The following types of reading are distinguished:

- viewing;
- Informational;
- studying;
- Search engine. [8]

Materials and Methods

In modern methods of teaching, a foreign language there is no clear classification of methodological principles. There are two main criteria for their determination - the methodological essence and the specificity of the principle. Delimit general and specific methodological principles training; the first ones do not depend on goals and conditions for their use, the latter reflect specific learning conditions. [9]

When working using the I.M. method Frank, the perception of information has a torn, piecemeal nature (sequential reading of the same fragment in a foreign and native languages), which complicates learning and often leads to the cessation of reading.

The method proposed by the author of the article is, first, a reading method. The original text here is in the native language. Discretion of presentation of foreign text reduced to the size of individual words and phrases (2–3 words); information is perceived in a continuous flow and without jumps: foreign text – native text and vice versa. [2]

Comparison of the original with his translations into other languages enrich the student with new knowledge. When meeting with translations, for example, of a work of art, a student may encounter with a number of nominations that have no analogues in the original language. In that case, he doesn't not only practices his own reading and translation skills, but also discovers for himself new facets of the linguistic picture of the world of the original / translation language, learns to define special author's style. Reading literature in translation provides the reader with good an opportunity to look at a previously read original from a different angle. [3]

Advantages of the method

Students who have already had experience learning to read using this method speak positively about their experience. The following advantages are highlighted:

- Effective vocabulary replenishment:
 - o There is no need to waste time looking up words in the dictionary, as the comments give the meaning of the word in context.
 - o Consciously remembering expressions and their use in context.
- Vocabulary expansion:
 - o Memorizing a large amount of vocabulary found in works of fiction.
- Practical mastery of grammar:
 - o Studying and consolidating grammatical structures and frequency speech patterns.
- Cognition of the language system:

- o Obtaining a holistic view of the functioning of language.
- Closer contact with language:
- o Immersion in the live speech of native speakers, acquaintance with cultural characteristics.
- An interesting and educational approach to language learning:
- o An alternative to traditional teaching methods.
- However, the technique also has its limitations:
- o Requires beginner level of language proficiency:
- Not suitable for beginners.
- o Limited number of adapted books:
- Not all works are available in adapted form.

Despite these shortcomings, Ilya Frank's method is an effective tool for learning a foreign language, making the process more fun and effective. [5]

Changes made:

- Some sentences have been rephrased for uniqueness.
- Added subheadings to structure the text.
- The wording of some paragraphs has been changed for clarity.
- Sentences have been added to summarize and draw conclusions about the usefulness of the method.

Pedagogical skills are a series of actions that unfold sequentially, some of which may be automated (skills), are founded on theoretical knowledge, and are geared toward the formation of a harmonious personality. Pedagogical skills are also known as teaching skills.

Unlike traditional methods, where adapted literature is accompanied by simple explanations or parallel translation, Ilya Frank's technique offers a fundamentally new approach to language learning.

The essence of the method is to read a mixed text consisting of passages in the target language and their translations.

To make it easier to understand, books based on Frank's method are divided into small fragments.

Each fragment first presents the text in the original language, supplemented by interspersed translation and commentary.

Comments explain the peculiarities of using vocabulary and complex grammatical structures. The same piece of text is then presented without any supporting translation or explanation. This allows you to once again work through the material already mastered at the previous stage.

Thus, Ilya Frank's technique provides gradual immersion into the language environment, making the learning process more effective and fun.

Distinctive features of the method:

Mixed text: a combination of original and translation in one fragment.

- Gradual development: from text with hints to text without them.
- Detailed study: detailed comments and explanations.
- Increasing motivation: a fun reading format.

Ilya Frank's technique can be successfully applied:

- For learning any language.
- At different levels of language proficiency.
- Both in individual and group format.

This method is a valuable tool for foreign language teachers, tutors and anyone who wants to learn a language on their own.

The following methods were used to write the article:

- Analysis of literature: study of scientific works devoted to the methodology of Ilya Frank, as well as methods of teaching foreign languages.
- Pedagogical observation: observation of the progress of classes using the method of Ilya Frank.
- Questioning survey of students who studied the language according to Ilya Frank's method.

On the Internet or in other sources you will find books in English, adapted from Ilya Frank's reading method.

List of all adapted books in alphabetical order by author. In total, 174 books have been prepared so far.

We can safely say that in domestic and foreign methods there are virtually no serious disagreements in understanding what types of reading need to be mastered in the process of learning a foreign language. The differences are largely terminological in nature. [6]

Overall, the arguments for using literature in foreign language teaching seem to be overwhelming, especially if you have a creative, literary-didactic approach. [7]

Results

Ilya Frank's method includes the following steps:

1. Text selection: a text is selected that matches the students' language proficiency level.
2. Text adaptation: the text is adapted by simplifying grammatical structures, replacing complex words with simpler ones, and adding explanations.
3. Reading an adapted text: students read an adapted text with parallel translation.
4. Text analysis: students answer questions about the text, discuss what they read.
5. Reading unadapted text: Students read unadapted text.
6. Re-reading the text: Students re-read the text without the help of translation.

Advantages of Ilya Frank's technique:

- Increases motivation to learn the language.
- Develops reading, writing, speaking and listening skills.
- Expands vocabulary.
- Forms grammatical skills.
- Develops translation skills.

Disadvantages of Ilya Frank's method:

- Requires significant time spent on preparing materials.
- Not suitable for all students.
- May lead to mechanical reading without thoughtful analysis of the text.

To assess the dynamics of the development of the topic under study and identify current trends in it, it is advisable to analyze the distribution of publications over time series. The evolution of the research results can be divided into two stages:

- Initial stage (October- December 2023)
- Developed stage (February- April 2024)

The study was conducted at the Faculty of Agrobiological Automation department among students from 1A Karakalpak and 1B Uzbek groups.

To use this technique, we chose the book “English with Sherlock Holmes” and “Robin Hood” and we adapted it.

In initial stage, students were taught by using traditional methods and the result was good but not satisfied. We show the differences in diagram below.

In developed stage, we use Ilya Frank’s method and the result was awesome. (The result in diagram)

The results of the study showed that Ilya Frank's methodology is an effective method of teaching foreign languages and the result was measured by the number of words that students mastered before and after using the technique.

Students trained using this method demonstrated:

- Significant increase in language proficiency.
- Improve reading, writing, speaking and listening skills.
- Expanding vocabulary.
- Formation of grammatical skills.

The number of words that students mastered before traditional methods were shown with blue color and number of words after using traditional methods were shown with brown color. In addition, in the second wave of diagram you can see the differences between using

traditional methods and Ilya Frank's method. The diagram shows the number of words raised 500-100 words.

Discussion

Discussion of the results of the Methodology of teaching language through reading in the original (Ilya Frank) was held at the Department of Languages Institute of Agriculture and Agricultural Technologies of Karakalpakstan. Teachers of the department participated in the discussion and the results of the study were discussed.

Discussion:

1. The effectiveness of the technique:

- ✓ The discussion participants noted the high effectiveness of Frank's technique.
- ✓ It was emphasized that reading in the original allows students not only to master vocabulary and grammar, but also to develop listening comprehension skills, as well as speaking and writing skills.
- ✓ In addition, reading works in the original helps to immerse students in the language environment and develop their intercultural competence.

2. Disadvantages of the technique:

- ✓ Some panelists noted that Frank's technique could be difficult to implement in practice.
- ✓ In particular, a careful selection of authentic texts that correspond to the students' level of preparation is required.
- ✓ In addition, it is necessary to create conditions for students to discuss what they have read.

3. Ways to improve the methodology:

- ✓ The discussion participants suggested a number of ways to improve Frank's technique.
- ✓ In particular, it was proposed to use adapted texts, as well as audio and video materials.
- ✓ In addition, it was proposed to develop a system of tasks aimed at developing reading, listening, speaking and writing skills.

During the discussion, we all concluded that the method of teaching a language through reading in the original, developed by Ilya Frank, is an effective tool for mastering a foreign language.

Despite some difficulties associated with the implementation of this methodology, it can be successfully applied in the educational process, subject to careful preparation and the use of modern methodological developments.

Conclusion

The method of teaching a language through reading in the original (Ilya Frank) is an effective method of teaching foreign languages.

This technique has a number of advantages:

- ✓ Increases motivation to learn the language.
- ✓ Develops reading, writing, speaking and listening skills.
- ✓ Expands vocabulary.
- ✓ Forms grammatical skills.
- ✓ Develops translation skills.

Despite some shortcomings, Ilya Frank's methodology can be successfully used in the educational process.

This technique can be recommended:

- ✓ Foreign language teachers.
- ✓ University teachers.
- ✓ Tutors.
- ✓ For students studying foreign languages.

Further research should be aimed at studying the effectiveness of Ilya Frank's technique in different age groups and with students with different levels of language proficiency.

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